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The End of an Era: Maharaja Ranjit Singh's Demise

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Abstract

The time was ripe for Maharaja Ranjit Singh and he was ripe for the time. He, in consequence, adventured upon the path of glory at an age when usually a boy born in the most fortuitous circumstances has hardly learnt to cipher. From martial success, reinforced by diplomatic astuteness, he rose to Kingship. He whose patrimony had been a tiny mud fort in a town that, till then, few persons had heard of, became, in less than three score years, the unquestioned arbiter of a state that stretched from the deserts of Rajputana to the passes provided by Nature for purposes of communication in the mountain chain with which she has girl India's north-west corner.

Keywords Ripe, Adventured, Circumstances, Kingship, Patrimony, Stretched.

Introduction

Punjab looked like a jigsaw puzzle consisting of fourteen pieces with five arrows piercing it from the sides in the end of 18th century. Twelve of these fourteen pieces were the Sikh misls; the other two were the Pathan and George Thomas. The five arrows were the Afghans in the north-west; the Rajputs of Kangra in the north; the Gurkhas in the north-east; the British in the east; and the Marathas in the south-east. At that time Sukerchakia Misl was becoming powerful in Punjab. On 13th November 1780, Ranjit Singh was born. He was the only son of Maha Singh, Sardar of Sukerchukia misl. His mother Raj Kaur was the daughter of Sardar Gajpat Singh, of state Jind. The child was named Budh Singh when the news of the birth of a son was brought to Maha Singh, who was returning from a victorious campaign against the chatta along the river Jhelum. With prophetic vision, he changed his son's name from Budh Singh, the wise one, to Ranjit Singh, the winner of battles. Festivities were held and the poor were given alms in the whole of the town for several days.

Objective of study

1. To inquire the early life of Maharaja Ranjit Singh.
2. To Study the most trust worthy nobles during Maharaja Ranjit Singh's last breath.
3. To provide information about last time of Maharaja Ranjit Singh.

Review of Literature

Suri, Sohan Lal (1968), "Umdat-Ut-Tawarikh" Daftar II, This book provides good knowledge about life and the vast empire expanded by Maharaja Ranjit Singh. It also gives information about the positions and social lives of the nobles in the Kingdom of Lahore. This book is preferred by every scholar who researches the Kingdom of Lahore.

Chopra, G.L. (1975), "The Panjab as a Sovereign State" informs about the civil and military administration of Maharaja Ranjit Singh and how he introduced many reforms in his administration. The writer also discusses the early and the last days of Maharaja Ranjit Singh's life.

Main Text

The child was attacked by smallpox at a very young age, and with the disease taking an unfavorable turn, his life was endangered. According to Asian custom, the father made large donations to the poor in charity, fed multitudes of Brahmins and holy men to secure their prayers, and sent gifts to the sacred temples at Kangra and Jwalamukhi. The boy

recovered, but with the ailment, he lost one of his eyes. No one could say at that time that the child with one eye was going to one day be the light of millions of his countrymen, who would be proud to bow to him in loyalty. Ranjit Singh was sent to learn reading and writing at the age of about six years. Sohan Lal mentions that Ranjit was entrusted to the care of one Bhai Phagu Singh Dharamsalia of Gujranwala for learning the Gurmukhi characters. But the young pupil paid no attention to his studies and would not even learn the alphabet.

Young Ranjit Singh accompanied his father on expeditions. Once he joined his father in an attack on Manchar. It was a fort which belonged to the Chatthas, old rivals of the family of Ranjit Singh. Mahan Singh's army laid siege to the fort. All of a sudden, Hashmat Khan, the uncle of the Chattha chief, climbed on the elephant carrying Ranjit Singh. Ranjit Singh showed great presence of mind. Before Hashmat Khan could lay his hands on him, he struck him down with his sword. Mahan Singh felt very proud to know of his son's valour and so were all his soldiers. Ranjit Singh was then scarcely ten years of age.

In the battle of Randpura near Batala between Jai Singh Kanahya and Maha Singh Sukarchakia. Jai Singh's eldest and ablest son, Gurbaksh Singh was killed. He left his widow, Sada Kaur and a little daughter, Mehtab Kaur. Maha Singh was at that time the rising star among all the Sikh chiefs. Sada Kaur was a farsighted lady, and had much of statesmanship in her. In one year's time she forgot the enmity existing between the Kanahya and Sukarchakia Misls. She secured the approval of her father-in-law, Jai Singh Kanahya, to cement an alliance between the two discordant families by offering Mehtab Kaur in marriage to Ranjit Singh. Sada Kaur learnt that Mahan Singh's wife Raj Kaur had gone to Jawalamukhi on a pilgrimage for the recovery of Ranjit Singh from smallpox. Sada Kaur immediately went there and persuaded her to accept her daughter for Ranjit Singh. On Ranjit Singh's recuperation, Mahan Singh held a grand feast at Gujranwala, Jai Singh Kanahya attended it, and made a formal proposal for a matrimonial alliance between the two houses.

Sardar Maha Singh, who had laid siege to the fort of Sohdra, where Sardar Sahib Singh Bhangi of Gujrat had taken shelter after refusing to pay tribute to the Sukerchakias, was suddenly fell very ill with dysentery. He appointed his twelve years old son Ranjit Singh as the head of misl in his own place, put him in command of his forces and returned to Gujranwala. Sardar Karam Singh Duloo of Chineot and Sardar Jodh Singh Bhangi were on their way to help Sahib Singh. Ranjit Singh staged a surprise attack on them, near Kot Maharaja, before they had reached their destination. Karam Singh and Jodh Singh were defeated and they ran from the field. Ranjit Singh, therefore, raised the siege of Sohdra returned to Gujranwala but he was too late to meet his father before the latter died. Managing an estate was not an easy for a boy as winning a battle. Ranjit Singh let his fathers's manager, Lakhpat Rai, continue in charge of the estate and his mother also supported Lakhpat Rai but her brother, Dal Singh, wished to throw him out and take his place. He found a ready ally as Sada Kaur, Ranjit Singh's mother-in-law to be, who kept intriguing from Batala, with occasional visits to Gujranwala. Ranjit Singh was just over fifteen years of age when he left Gujranwala for Batala, the chief town of the Kanhyas, to wed Mehtab Kaur. This alliance between the two important Sikh families was a major event for the Punjab. All the leading Sikh chiefs were present at the wedding. Ranjit Singh's mind was now completely obsessed with visions of power. Experience of the previous campaign had proved to him that Kanhayas were not as strong as he had believed. His chances would be brighter if he could draw some other misl on his side. He made overtures to the chief of the Nakkais and married Raj Kaur. She was the sister of the Nakkai Sardar. This marriage proved to be more successful than the first.

There was another significant incident that had happened in this year. Diwan Lakhpat Rai (Lakhoo) was killed in the Dhanni territory. Ranjit Singh, too, had completed his eighteenth year. He, now, took charge of the administration of the state directly in his hand and appointed Sardar Dal Singh, as his minister.

On the 1st of Baisakh (12 April), 1801, a royal durbar was held inside the fort for the celebration of the occasion. The gentry of the town—Hindus, Sikhs, and Muslims—declared him to be the Maharaja of Punjab. Baba Sahib Singh Bedi made the colored mark of the Maharaja ship on the forehead of Ranjit Singh. The citizens showered flower petals on the heads of their favorite rulers. A royal salute was fired from the fort. In the afternoon, the young Maharaja rode on his elephant, showering gold and silver coins on the jubilant crowds of his subjects. In the evening, all the homes in the city were illuminated. Maharaja Ranjit Singh was to be called the Sarkar (Lord). The currency of the Sikh Raj, the Nanak-Shahi Coins, was put into circulation the same day.

The far-sighted statesman and the most courageous Maharaja Ranjit Singh had consolidated the scattered small Sikh territories and laid firm foundations of the Khalsa

Raj. He had increased his power and strength to such an extent that on one side, the British authorities in India and the Pathan rulers of Kabul, Kandhar acknowledged his supremacy. But ultimately this distinguished monarch's life came to an end.

In 1835, Maharaja Ranjit Singh had a stroke which paralyzed his right side and seriously affected his speech. His face became distorted and his tongue could not move. The physical paralysis brought depression in its wake. However, Fakir Aziz-ud-din helped him to recover a part of his articulation. A complicating factor was his aversion to western drugs and observing the doctor's directions. He insisted on going out in the morning even after fever had laid him low during the night, and he would hold his durbar as usual even though it was very difficult to follow what he said. A second attack of paralysis overpowered him about a year and a half later. This left him, more or less, an invalid. It affected the right side once again and his speech became still more inarticulate. He had to be lifted on the saddle when he wanted to have a ride. After some months he felt little relief from this disease.

In June 1839 the Governor General Lord Auckland came Lahore to meet the Maharaja, who held a grand Durbar in Shalimar Bagh. A number of Rajas and Nawabs were invited to the reception, the festivities continued for days. In the course of these celebrations, one day the Maharaja was suddenly taken ill while sitting in his chair. His body shook terribly and for few moments, it seemed that he collapsed, his head tilted and rested against the back of the chair. The eyes became stony and motionless. He could not utter a word and water started flowing from his mouth. The physicians from Amritsar, Lahore and other places held conferences. A doctor was sent by the British government. Dr. Honigberger, his personal physician, also attended him. But nothing seemed to avail. He became very weak and difficult to speech.

At last, Lion of Punjab realized that his death days were near so he held the Durbar in the Hazoori Garden. This was his last session with his nobility. He reached the Durbar where he was taken in a palanquin. He put a sandal mark on the forehead of Prince Kharak Singh in token of his being the successor of the Maharaja from that day. He next made Dhian Singh Dogra grasp the hand of the Prince as a promise, on the part of the former, of loyalty to the new King. The citation of Prince Kharak Singh being the Maharaja and Dhian Singh Dogra the Chief Minister was proclaimed then.

Amount of more than twenty-five lakhs of rupees was given away in alms to the poor. A jagir of twenty-five thousand rupees was fixed for the Shri Darbar Sahib at Amritsar. Offering were made at mosques and temples in Lahore. The Maharaja ordered his personal horses and elephants should send to Amritsar. On 27 June 1839, was a dark night, Maharaja Ranjit Singh laid on his sick-bed in the Samman Burj of the Lahore fort. He moved his lips and rolled his one eye to look at things around him. He was nearing his death, while his generals, with whom he had won such magnificent victories, watched helplessly. There were tears in the eyes of them all. They had all been ordinary men, had been raised to nobility and riches by Maharaja Ranjit Singh. Once anyone caught Maharaja Ranjit Singh's eye he rose in stature. Now the Maharaja was alone, struggling against death. His generals could not provide him any help. Hakim sat by his bedside, deeply worried. Maharaja Ranjit Singh made a sign that he should be seated in a chair and this was immediately done. Dr. Honigberger in his book Thirty Five Years in the East has thus described the scene;

“The Maharaja was seated in chair. He was paralyzed and could not move. He had lost the power of speech. He could only communicate his wishes through gestures of his hands. He had no other way, because he was illiterate.”

The Maharaja breathed his last in the Samman Burj. Exactly forty years earlier he had ridden into the fort. He said goodbye to the world. No kitchen fires were lit in Lahore on that day. The entire Kingdom was grief-stricken. The gates of the fort were ordered by Dhian Singh Dogra to be closed, and the news of the death not made public till arrangements for the funeral obsequies were made. The Ranis, maid-servants, Kanwar Kharak Singh, Dhian Singh Dogra and many other sobbed like children, raised their voices in lamentation, tore off their hair, put earth on their heads, struck them against walls. This continued during the whole night by the side of the corpse. But the dreadful news reached in the people. A wave of shock and grief swept among them. There was mourning in every home. Maharaja Ranjit Singh had been very popular as a ruler. Everyone felt as though he or she had lost a kin. No ruler ever could lay claim to the love and admiration that the people of Punjab showered on Maharaja Ranjit Singh. The reason simply was that the Maharaja loved his people as his own children.

On the next day Kharak Singh bathed and with the help of nobility Maharaja Ranjit Singh on wooden stool and gave him bath with Ganga water. After that Maharaja was dressed

up with ornaments. All the nobility and near ones presented his doshalas. People from Lahore city was gathered for Maharaja's last darshan.

The bier was then carried by the grief-stricken princes and sardars to the Hazuri Bagh. The body was placed on the pyre and the guns fired the last salute to the great Maharaja. Soon the flames were leaping up to the skies. The man, who by his energy and wisdom had created out of chaos a strong and well-administered state and who had conferred upon the people the gifts of unity, peace and freedom, was no more. Twenty-two lakhs of rupees in cash and goods worth twenty-five lakhs of rupees were given in charity to the needy. That was how that brave warrior disappeared from this mundane world, leaving behind him an unforgettable trial of a glorious memory on the firmament of the history of this country.

According to the prevailing customs the ashes of the Maharaja, were collected and dispatched in palanquin to Haridwar for immersion in the waters of the Ganga. The bag containing the ashes was placed before Holy Granth and then on the palanquin in which Maharaja Ranjit Singh used to ride. The mounted bodyguard of the Maharaja, a corps of 2000 cavalry, together with two infantry battalions, marched in front of the palanquin, while the Princes and chiefs followed after, and then came elephants and lines of horses. As the procession emerged from the Taxali Gate of the city. Writes Munshi Sohan Lal, "the guns from the ramparts of the fort and city walls fired the first salute." This was followed by a second salvo when it passed through the Delhi Gate, on to the Trunk Road. The five-mile route from the Delhi Gate to the Shalimar Gardens was lined by seven thousand of the elite corps of infantry, cavalry and artillery. As the palanquin passed, each unit presented arms. The last salute was given near the Shalimar Gardens. Then the Chiefs returned to the city leaving the remains of their departed master in the charge of Bhai Gurmukh Singh, Sardar Dhana Singh Malwai and Rattan Singh Gadwai, who were appointed to accompany them towards destination. Sohan Lal relates that as the remains of the Maharaja passed through the estates of his own chiefs and then through territories of other Indian Prince and the British, ceremonial offering of presents and nazranas, salutes by guards of honor was observed as it had been during his lifetime with the ceremony of Kirya on the thirteenth day, the period of mourning came to an end.

Maharaja Ranjit Singh is dead, poor fellow! And died as like the old Lion as he had lived. He preserved his senses to the last, and was (which is unusual with native princes) obeyed to the last by all his nobility.

Conclusion

In the conclusion, author can say that Maharaja Ranjit Singh, who had not lost any battle on the earth but at the end of his life he lost his battle of breath due to his health issues. But he still lives in the memories of people not only in Punjab also around the world.

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